

SMART GRIDS AND THE GREEN ECONOMY

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Abstract. *The development of a green economy requires innovative approaches to energy generation, distribution, and consumption. Smart grids, as advanced energy networks, play a fundamental role in this transition by integrating renewable energy sources, enhancing energy efficiency, and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. By combining digital technologies, automation, and real-time data management, smart grids enable more flexible and sustainable energy systems. They facilitate demand response, improve the reliability of supply, and support the large-scale use of solar, wind, and other renewable resources. This paper examines the role of smart grids in the green economy, their contribution to low-carbon development, and the challenges associated with implementation, including regulatory frameworks, investment requirements, and technological barriers. The findings suggest that smart grids are not only a technological innovation but also a strategic driver of sustainable development in the 21st century.*

Keywords. *Smart grids; green economy; renewable energy; sustainable development; energy efficiency; low-carbon transition; energy distribution; digital technologies.*

Аннотация. *Яшил иқтисодиётни ривожлантириши энергия ишлаб чиқариши, тақсимот ва истеъмолда инновацион ёндашувларни талаб қилади. Замонавий электр тармоқлари сифатидаги ақлли тармоқлар ушбу жараёнда асосий ўрин тутиб, янгиланадиган энергия манбаларини интеграция қилиши, энергия самарадорлигини ошириши ва иссиқхона газлари чиқиндиларини камайтиришида муҳим аҳамиятга эга. Рақамли технологиялар, автоматлаштириши ва реал вақтда маълумотларни бошқариши орқали ақлли тармоқлар янада барқарор ва мослашувчан энергия тизимларини таъминлайди. Улар талабга жавоб қайтариши механизмларини йўлга қўйиб, таъминот ишончилигини оширади ва қуёш, шамол каби янгиланадиган манбалардан кенг қўламда фойдаланиши имконини беради. Ушбу мақолада яшил иқтисодиётда ақлли тармоқларнинг роли, кам углеродли ривожланишга қўшган ҳиссаси ҳамда амалга ошириши билан боғлиқ муаммолар — меъёрий-ҳуқуқий асослар, инвестиция талаблари ва технология тўсиқлари таҳлил қилинади. Хулосалар шуни кўрсатадики, ақлли тармоқлар нафақат технологиявий янгилик, балки XXI асрда барқарор ривожланишнинг стратегик ҳаракатлантирувчиси ҳисобланади.*

Калим сўзлар. *Ақлли тармоқлар; яшил иқтисодиёт; янгиланадиган энергия; барқарор ривожланиши; энергия самарадорлиги; кам углеродли ўтиши; энергия тақсимоти; рақамли технологиялар.*

Аннотация. *Развитие «зелёной» экономики требует инновационных подходов к производству, распределению и потреблению энергии. Интеллектуальные сети, как современная форма электрических сетей, играют ключевую роль в этом процессе, обеспечивая интеграцию возобновляемых источников энергии, повышение энергоэффективности и сокращение выбросов парниковых газов. С помощью цифровых технологий, автоматизации и управления данными в реальном времени*

интеллектуальные сети позволяют формировать более устойчивые и гибкие энергосистемы. Они внедряют механизмы отклика на спрос, повышают надёжность энергоснабжения и обеспечивают широкомасштабное использование возобновляемых ресурсов, таких как солнечная и ветровая энергия. В данной статье рассматривается роль интеллектуальных сетей в «зелёной» экономике, их вклад в низкоуглеродное развитие, а также проблемы внедрения, включая нормативно-правовые основы, инвестиционные требования и технологические барьеры. Сделанные выводы показывают, что интеллектуальные сети являются не только технологическим новшеством, но и стратегическим драйвером устойчивого развития в XXI веке.

Ключевые слова. *Интеллектуальные сети; зелёная экономика; возобновляемая энергия; устойчивое развитие; энергоэффективность; низкоуглеродный переход; распределение энергии; цифровые технологии.*

Over the past two decades, a new trend has emerged in the global economy — the “green” economy, or ecological economics, which ensures the sustainable development of states and may serve as a means of protecting humanity from the threats of the environmental crisis¹. In this context, specialized literature increasingly employs concepts such as “smart city,” “smart home,” and “smart grid.” According to the European Smart website, as a result of the economic and technological changes driven by globalization, European cities have faced the following challenge: how to combine economic competitiveness with environmental protection.

A smart home is a modern type of residential building that provides comfortable living through the automation of its services. It implies a system designed to ensure comfort (including safety) and resource efficiency for all users². Smart power grids (hereafter referred to as smart grids) are modernized networks that employ information and communication technologies to collect data on energy production and consumption. This enables the automatic improvement of efficiency, reliability, economic benefits, as well as the sustainability of electricity generation and distribution³. The development of smart grids takes place within the framework of the “green” economy, which integrates many spheres of human life and activity. One of the sectors of the green economy is “green” energy, which, in addition to renewable energy sources, includes cogeneration (the combined production of electricity and heat). However, sources of electrical energy cannot exist without the infrastructure that consists of means for transmission, distribution, and management of energy. The transmission of electrical energy involves power lines and equipment for the conversion of electrical energy. It is smart technologies that make it possible to improve the infrastructure related to the transmission and management of electricity supply to consumers. In other words, the objectives of creating smart grids are to enhance the reliability of electricity supply to consumers, to establish the infrastructure of the retail electricity market, and to enable effective management of energy costs.

Environmental Benefits of Smart Grid Development. Today, there are virtually no government institutions that fail to recognize the necessity of applying smart technologies, which is reflected in national development strategies. For example, state-owned electricity grid companies are expected to adopt smart technologies in order to improve energy efficiency and reduce costs. At the same time, it should be noted that the development of smart grids is

¹ Лившиц В. Зеленая экономика. URL: <http://www.proza.ru/2013/02/19/2075>.

² Умный дом. URL: https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/%D3%EC%ED%FB%E9_%E4%EE%EC.

³ Умные сети электроснабжения. URL: <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>

constrained by low electricity tariffs set by the state, primarily for political reasons, which prevents capital recovery in the short term. In addition, there are no budgetary sources of financing for the creation and development of smart cities, including the infrastructure needed to ensure a decent living environment for citizens.

Despite the advantages associated with the use of smart grids, private investors have so far been reluctant to channel investments into state-owned monopoly organizations. Nevertheless, without the development of smart grids it is impossible to improve citizens' quality of life, create competitive energy markets, and attract investors to related business sectors.

For a comprehensive assessment of the environmental benefits of smart grid development, it is necessary to examine the very process of electricity transmission and distribution from the perspective of the physical essence of the technology and to evaluate its effects. The technology of electricity transmission and distribution, known as the technological consumption of electricity for its transportation or technical losses, implies the use of part of the generated electricity. In modern practice, this technological consumption is referred to as loss compensation by electricity grid companies.

Within the cost structure of electricity transmission and distribution services, expenses for loss compensation can account for up to 50% of total costs. The electricity classified as technical losses is purchased by territorial grid companies (hereafter TGCs) on the wholesale market, directly from suppliers, and in some cases from energy producers. It is also possible for TGCs to use self-generated electricity to compensate for technical losses; however, under current technological conditions, this option is more expensive than purchasing electricity. At the same time, the use of renewable energy sources is regarded as a promising direction for compensating losses within smart grids.

Electricity losses in Uzbekistan's distribution grids account for 14–16% or more of the net supply, which is significantly higher than the comparable indicator for foreign companies (6–8%). Moreover, there are substantial regional differences in the level of losses, with the highest rates observed in regions characterized by high levels of household consumption⁴.

At the same time, technical losses in high-voltage transmission lines are not considered due to their relatively small scale and the advanced technological level of electricity transmission. Consequently, through the implementation of smart grid development measures, it is possible to plan for technical losses at the level of leading countries, namely around 4–5%. For example, electricity transmission losses amount to 4% in the Netherlands, 5.0% in Germany, 5.2% in Japan, 6.9% in Italy, 7.2% in the United States, and 7.8% in France.

At present, it is not yet possible to abandon the transportation functions, nor the significant number of controllers, electricians, and technicians working in territorial grid companies (TGCs), who are obliged to perform the following operational functions on-site:

- detecting illegal connections to the networks and equipment of TGCs engaged in the transmission and distribution of electricity;
- recording electricity meter readings;
- monitoring electricity loads;
- regulating voltage levels;

⁴ “Strategy for the Development of Distribution Electric Networks in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2025” (13 pages)

- preparing electricity and capacity balances;
- redistributing connected loads;
- calculating energy consumption among unmetered customers based on contractual values or established norms, etc.

In the future, all of these functions will be performed within smart grids without direct human involvement, except for scheduled maintenance and reconstruction.

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that smart grids are directly related to green energy and will contribute to improving environmental protection.